

PARTIAL REPLACEMENT OF XANTHATE BY ORGANOSOLV LIGNIN ON PYRITE/ARSENOPYRITE FLOTATION

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ABSTRACT – Since xanthates are toxic chemicals that are eventually disposed to the environment, the utilization of chemical collectors during the flotation of pyrite and arsenopyrite raises concerns about the sustainability of the process. The partial substitution of xanthate collectors with bio collector lignin turns out to be a viable option. In this study, we investigate the potentiality of lignin micro and nanoparticles to be used as collectors in the flotation process, focusing on the application of different collectors' mixtures (SIPX/lignin). It was found out that a 50% replacement of SIPX is viable, leading to improvement of pyrite/arsenopyrite grade and recovery in concentrate.

Keywords: Pyrite, Flotation, Lignin, Collector, Selectivity.

INTRODUCTION

The recovery of pyrite and arsenopyrite from mixed sulphide ore originated from Halkidiki, Greece is of interest due to its gold content. The use of traditional collectors such as xanthates to generate a bulk concentrate made up of pyrite and arsenopyrite have been achieved with relative ease and often the practice [1]. Both minerals are readily floatable with several type of collectors like xanthates, dithiophosphates and fatty acids [2]. Despite their efficiency, xanthates possess negative environmental impact. Also, their production is centralized in China, while the frequent quality deviations affect the efficiency of separation [3]. There is an increasing trend in the development and use of eco-friendly chemicals in the flotation process [4,5].

Lignin is an abundant and low-cost material obtained from forest residues and side streams of the pulp industry, and it has been shown that, lignin micro- and nanoparticles can be used as collectors in copper recovery by froth flotation process [6]. In the current study, we investigate the potentiality of the use of lignin nano and microparticles as collectors in pyrite and arsenopyrite flotation, aiming partial replacement of xanthates. In this frame, various xanthate/lignin proportion mixtures were prepared and used in the flotation of mixed sulphide ore aiming the recovery of pyrite and arsenopyrite.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Lignin preparation

The lignin of wood chips from birch and spruce was first extracted with organosolv

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and then used to make lignin nanoparticles. The birch woodchips were prepared at 183 °C for 1 hour in a 50% v/v ethanol in water solution whereas the spruce woodchips were pretreated at the same temperature in a 60% v/v ethanol in water solution before allowing it to dissolve in a mixture of 75% ethanol and water, drying the separated lignin [7]. Using a pressure homogenizer, 5% w/v of the lignin in the ethanol/water solution was then homogenized at 750 bars. The homogenized liquid was further diluted with deionized water, which resulted in the formation of nanoparticles. To create dry powdered nanoparticles, the material was freeze dried.

Chemical and mineralogical analyses

The sample used in the experiments was obtained from the production line of HellasGold facility at Olympiada, Chalkidiki. It is the residue (tailing) after the implementation of two consecutive flotation stages targeting the selection of galena and sphalerite. Indeed, as shown in **Table 1**, the sample presents very low Pb and Zn content. As for the granulometry of the sample, it is size of $d_{80}=193$.

Table 1 Total Oxide X-Ray Analysis with X-Ray Fluorescence Spectrometer of Au feed

Oxide	Content (%)
PbO	0.50
ZnO	0.66
Fe ₂ O ₃	16.67
As ₂ O ₃	7.60
S	11.31
Sb	0.02
CuO	0.03
C	3.54
MgO	2.11
Al ₂ O ₃	4.57
SiO ₂	19.94
K ₂ O	1.06
CaO	14.76
MnO	1.07
Loss On Ignition	13.80
Other	2.36
Total	100

According to modal analysis presented in **Table 2**, approx. 22 wt. % of the sample consists of pyrite and arsenopyrite.

Table 2 Modal mineralogical analysis

Mineral	Content (%)
Galena (PbS)	0.53
Sphalerite (ZnS)	0.79
Pyrite (FeS)	13.64
Arsenopyrite (FeAsS)	8.74

Flotation Experiments

CuSO₄ was utilized as activator for the flotation of pyrite/arsenopyrite at a concentration of around 170 g/t. Additionally, sodium isopropyl xanthate (SIPX) and lignin were added as collectors in two phases; 80% of the collector was added at the conditioning stage and the remaining 20% right after the end of the rougher flotation stage. Dowfroth was used as a frother, while H₂SO₄ served as a pH regulator. **Table 3** demonstrates the pH and the duration of each processing stage. The trials were conducted with a stirring speed of 1500 rpm.

Table 3 Pyrite/arsenopyrite circuit pH and time schedule

Stages	pH	Conditioning min	Froth min
Conditioning	6.8-7.5	5	
Rougher	6.8-7.5		5
Scavenger 1	7.2-8.2	1	7
Scavenger 2	7.2-8.2		6

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 depicts Au and Pb grade and recovery in the concentrate obtained by applying different collector composition. On the control trial, where solely SIPX was used as collector, Au recovery reached 90.7% while the recovery of gangue (Pb) was at 61.4%. In case were solely lignin was used as collector, Au recovery dropped drastically to 11.8% and Pb recovery was 40.5%. The results are much improved when SIPX/lignin mixture was sued as collector; when the 50/50 wt.% mixture of collectors was applied, Au recovery exceeded 96%, which is also the case for Pb which recovery reached 68.5%.

Figure 1 Xanthate partial replacement with lignin (180 g/t) graph

The selectivity index (SI) was developed by Gaudin as a valuable metric for the evaluation two-way separation and collectors' selectivity [8]. It is defined as:

$$SI = \sqrt{\frac{Rv \times Rg}{(100 - Rv) \times (100 - Rg)}} \quad (1)$$

where R_v % is the recovery of Au in the flotation concentrate, and R_g % is the recovery of gangue (Pb) in the tailing fraction. SI takes into account two parameters: the recovery of precious minerals in the concentrate and the recovery of gangue minerals in the tailing. Another, criterion for evaluating the results is also the separation efficiency (SE), which is use for assessing the separation process [9].

$$SE = R_a - R_b \quad (2)$$

where R_a and R_b are the recoveries of valuable and gangue minerals in the concentrate respectively.

Table 4 presents Au and Pb recovery in concentrates and SE and SI values. SI for the control sample is 3.9 and drops to 3.3 when lignin is added by 50% followed with minor difference in Pb recovery. Also, the SE falls from 29.6 to 27.1. For sole lignin, the calculated SE and SI factors inform about the poor separation thus informing that only partial replacement of SIPX is viable.

Table 4 Selectivity Index and Separation Efficiency parameters [Collector dos: 180 g/t]

Collector composition	Au recovery in concentrate, R_{vAu} (%)	Pb recovery in concentrate, R_{bPb} (%)	Separation Efficiency (SE)	Selectivity Index (SI)
SIPX 100 %	91	61.4	29.6	3.9
SIPX/BN 50/50 %	96	68.9	27.1	3.3
SIPX/BN 50/100 %	96	68.5	27.5	3.3
Birch Nano 100%	12	40.5	28.5	0.4

At the second series of experiments, the collector dosage was increased from 180 g/t to 200 g/t. **Figure 2** presents Au and Pb grade and recovery for different collector composition. The results confirmed the findings of the previous series of separation experiments; 50% replacement of SIPX is viable, since Au grade and recovery are equal or higher compared to the control sample where solely xanthate is used.

Figure 2 Xanthate partial replacement with lignin (200 g/t) graph

Comparing the data presented in **Figure 2** and **Figure 1**, for 50/50 % collector composition, the results are in agreement; Au recoveries from the concentrate were 96.4 % to 94.6 %, and Pb recovery were 68.9% to 69.8% for collector dosage of 180 and 200 g/t, respectively.

Table 5 presents SE and SI values for the separation experiments presented in **Figure 2**.

Table 5 SI and SE parameters for Pyrite/Arsenopyrite separation using different collector compositions [Collector dosage: 200 g/t]

Collector composition	Au recovery in concentrate, R_{vAu} (%)	Pb recovery in tailing, R_{gPb} (%)	Pb recovery in concentrate, R_{bPb} (%)	Separation Efficiency (SE)	Selectivity Index (SI)
SIPX 100 %	94.4	23.2	76.8	17.6	2.3
SIPX/BN 75/25 %	96.5	22.9	77.1	19.4	2.9
SIPX/BN 50/50 %	94.6	30.2	69.8	24.8	2.8
SIPX/BN 25/75 %	90.4	28.5	71.5	18.9	1.9
SIPX/BN 90/45 %	95.6	31.5	68.5	27.1	3.2

Overall, the best performance is achieved for collector composition SIPX/BN 90/45 % (270 g/t collector) where SE and SI values were 27.1 and 3.2, respectively. However, those results are comparable to the results obtained by using SIPX/BN 50/50% collector composition.

CONCLUSIONS

This study was focused on the use of lignin as collector in the recovery of both pyrite and arsenopyrite from mixed sulfides through froth flotation process. The experiments were conducted to materials obtained from Olympias processing plant, Halkidiki, Greece and were previously treated for recovery of galena and sphalerite. In comparison to the case where solely SIPX was used, a 50% replacement of SIPX by lignin nanoparticles led to an increase of both Au grade and recovery from 17.8 to 18.9 g/t and from 90.7% to 96.4%, respectively. For the same replacement ratio, both SE and SI values were found as 27.1 and 3.3, respectively. From those preliminary results it can be shown that lignin can partially replace SIPX without affection of the separation efficiency. Moreover, it is expected that, the use of lignin can increase the Au recovery, provided that the separation will take place under the optimum application conditions.

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